

Healthy Life Style and Life Style Risks of Rural Adolescents

Dr. N. Sukumaran

*Assistant Professor, Department of Sociology
Government Arts and Science College, Sankarankovil
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Abstract

Health is an important output for the human development resources and the quality of life, and there by the overall development of the country. Healthy life style leaves the individual fit, energetic and at reduced risk for disease, based on the choices individual make about his daily habits. Good nutrition, daily exercise and adequate sleep are the foundation for remaining in good health. The information was obtained from the respondents on awareness and knowledge of personal hygiene, impact of open defecation, regular exercises, sound sleep, dental care, balanced diet, correct bodyweight, obey health norms, use fresh foods and limiting sedentary activities etc. The present study aims to understand the socio-cultural influence on family health particularly adolescents personality development and health behaviour. The present study was carried out in cuddalore district in Tamil Nadu.

Keywords: *Living Conditions, Life Style, Health Care Practice, Healthy Behaviour, Personal Hygiene*

Introduction

Human health is multi factorial. Socio-Cultural factors such as imagination, acculturation and Social support play a significant role in health attribution and medical adherence. The most important determinants of health are Heredity, Environment, Life Style, Socio- Economic conditions and health and Family Welfare Services. The complex system of life style environment and health status of human being are interred related. Adolescence is a period which comprises of stress and strain, storm and strife. Human health status is determined primarily by their social network (Culture, family history, education occupation and income) lifestyle (living conditions and patterns of behavior) health care behaviours, disease risk factors, health care environment and physical environment.

Adolescents today are under enormous academic, Social and digital pressure that affects their quality of life. They need holistic health with physical, emotional, mental and social well being for their balanced develop merit physical health is very important for a growing child. A well balanced diet provides proteins, Vitamins and Minerals to boost immunity and overall health and personal development. The rural home rules place a strong emphasis on the value of eating home cooked, freshly prepared meals. Maintain an active lifestyle requires promoting physical activities focused in homes.

Adolescence stage of human life is span of growth and development. Maximum growth of height is reached and thinking power, critical observation, logical reasoning and intelligence also reach the maximum emotional instability will be there. The period of stress and strain comes in the way. Regular physical activities in the family may help lower the risk of lifestyle disorders.

Problem Setting

Health is a capital that everyone has and it is the most precious to any creature in the universe, it influences all the deeds of human beings and shapes one's destiny. Adolescence is a stage of significant growth and development in which adequate nutrition to prevent health problems in adult life. Over the past three decades rapid economic growth with real gross domestic product has lifted millions out of

poverty. This, combined with government programmes, had led to improved health and development of the country youth, who account for almost 20 percent of the population.

In view of this, the present study has made attempt to study the health behaviour of adolescents and aims to understand how social factors influence the people particularly adolescent's in their health management / maintenance behavior. The researcher intended to carry out a study in two villages of Cuddalore District, Tamilnadu. Cuddalore district is one of the vulnerable districts in Tamilnadu in health aspect. In order to understand the adolescents health behavior and 'Social factor's' the present study aims at analyzing their extent of awareness and knowledge. Hygiene and sanitation, nutritional status, healthy life style, health education, health care and rescue factors for risks like style hazards.

Natural physiological changes take place during the puberty period in all the inner and outer organs of the body. But the puberty age depends upon the socio-economic status, standard of living, early or late marriages, and family heredity in case of girls.

Methods of Study

The present study aims to understand the Socio-Cultural influence on family health particularly adolescents personality development behavior. The present research was undertaken.

- To study the Socio-Cultural and health profile of the respondents.
- To understand the cultural influence, peer pressure and parental role on seeking care in maintaining healthcare of the respondents.
- To study the level of their awareness and knowledge on healthy lifestyle and rescue measures for life style risks,
- To study how the governmental health care services contribute to positive health of the adolescents in the study area.

Selection of the Study Area

Cuddalore district in Tamilnadu was selected for the present study. The major reasons for this selection are the social, physical and demographic condition of the district.

Sampling Design

Two villages were selected for this study namely Karaikadu and Manjakuzhi located at Cuddalore and Chidambaram taluk respectively. It was decided to select 15 per cent of the respondents, teenagers i.e, 314 respondents form two selected villages (adolescents, i.e., 13 to 19 years of age) are selected as sample by using purposive sampling method with a view to give relative importance to the adolescents of different socio-economic and cultural back ground.

Tools of Data Collection;

The researcher has collected the relevant data from the respondents by using a well interview schedule. The researcher visited each household and collected the data personally by establishing a good rapport with them. In addition to interviews, height and weight measurement were taken for all respondents to estimate there body mass index even though the respondents are vibrant mentality they extended full co-operation and in the opinion of the researcher their responses are fair and good.

Limitation of the Study:

The findings of the study are applicable only to rural respondents and they do not represent the rural respondents.

Data Analysis

The information obtained from the respondents were classified and arranged in order to understand the nature, pattern and attitudes of health management among adolescents in the study area. For this purpose, the researcher analysed the gathered data and classified it into 8 selections.

They are as follows. Socio-economic background of respondents, Food consumption Pattern, Growth and Development of Adolescence, Parental Care and Medical Care, Personal Hygiene and Sanitation, Habitual Activities /Aesthetic Life Style, Healthy Life Style, Government Health Services and Rescue Measures for life Style Risks.

Hippocrates said let food be your medicine'. Healthy food habits promote good health where as unhealthy food habits lead to illness and disease. It is widely recognized that the determinants of health are social and economic rather than purely medical. Health oriented behaviour does not pertain just to these activities concerned with recovering from disease or injury, but also involves the kinds of things that healthy people do to stay healthy. Human life is undergoing significant transition and change. Among the most affected are the adolescents due to social, cultural, psychological, technological and economical influences.

Summary of Findings

Data derived from that analysis of socio-economic background of respondents. It is inferred that female respondents are outnumbered (165) than male. It indicated that sex ratio is highest while it compared with sex ratio of Tamil Nadu. Further the fact might be realized that female children taken as equal to male children thus the old panorama of female feticide and other antagonistic activities against the female children concern born and brought up by their parents.

It is found the present study that great number (41.4%) of respondents belongs to 17 to 19 years of old in the study area. It can also be concluded that the low age respondents are less number because of the impact of small family norm.

Table 1 Distribution of the Respondents by their Age

Age	Frequency	Per cent
Below 14	73	23.2
15-16	111	35.4
17 and Above	130	41.4
Total	314	100.0

As far as the caste group of the respondents is concerned the fact that of the total 64.3 per cent of them belong to MBC and comprised them dominant in the study area and 33.8 per cent of them belong to scheduled caste and the rest of very few (1.9%) are backward caste.

It is observed that all the educated and a significant number of respondents (161) are studying in high school, but very few of the respondents were drop out from their study of schooling level in the study area due to domestic reasons. It can be estimated from the study of the data that most of the respondents family (235-75.2%) have poor living worth because of low earning capacity i.e., below Rs. 25,000 as their annual income.

In this region the most of the respondents (188-59.7%) live in their thatched houses. Even thought the government for life poor people in the sector of green house, some area are not eligible to get the government housing scheme for constructing houses because of their economic paucity in the study area.

It is estimated from the study of the data that majority of the respondents food consumption is very sad and most of the respondents are not at all intake most of the essential nutritious food items such as cereals, fruits, greens, meat due to economic paucity and lack of adequate job opportunities.

It could be seen from the above study of data that there are only 83 respondents irrespective of their gender status and age have a high level knowledge, tremendous changes in their body and mind in the contemporary stage of life. It is proved by chi-square test towards significant association between

the respondent's age differentiation and their level of knowledge about growth and development of adolescence.

It is very clear from the study of the data that a considerable number (50) of high school level educated respondents are having a high level knowledge in their physical, cognitive, social and emotional changes during adolescence compared with other category educated respondents in the study area.

With respect to the caste rank and their level of knowledge on growth and development of adolescence, it is indicated that most of the MBC adolescents are having high level understanding on their body and mind changes during this period.

It could be witnessed from the study of the data that there are 61 respondents from the family monthly income category of Rs.25,000 /- to 35,000-, having well informed in their contemporary transitional stage of life. It is noted from the study of the data that there is no association between their annual family income and their level of knowledge in their metabolic, cognitive, social and emotional changes.

Table 2 Distribution of Gender Wise Respondents by their Views on Parents Care and Medical Care

Gender	Level of Affection And Care Taken			Total
	Low	Medium	High	
Male	23 (7.3%)	115 (36.6%)	11 (3.5%)	149 (47.5%)
Female	21 (6.7%)	135 (43.0%)	9 (2.9%)	165 (52.5%)
Total	44 (14.0%)	250 (79.6%)	20 (6.4%)	314 (100.0%)

Calculated Chi-square Value	Degrees of Freedom	Level of Significant
1.078	2	0.583 (Not Significant)

With the respect of respondents opinion on level of satisfaction of parental care and medical care, only 20 respondents irrespective their gender status are highly satisfied in their parental affinity and medical care during health disorder. However, it is observed that the gender discrimination.

Table 3 Distribution of Education Wise Respondents and their Level of Healthy Life Style Access

Education	Level of Access			Total
	Low	Medium	High	
Middle	0	26 (8.3%)	37(11.8%)	63 (20.1%)
High School	2 (0.6%)	47 (15.0%)	107 (34.1%)	156 (49.7%)
Higher Secondary	0	30 (9.6%)	57 (18.2%)	87 (27.7%)
College	0	4 (1.3%)	4 (1.3%)	8 (2.5%)
Total	2 (0.6%)	107 (34.1%)	205 (65.3%)	314 (100.0)

Calculated Chi-square Value	Degrees of Freedom	Level of Significant
5.258	6	0.511 (Not Significant)

It could be calculated from the above study of the table that a good majority of the respondents (65.3%) irrespective of their educational status are having a high level awareness, knowledge and adoption of healthy life style practices for their happy long life.

The computed Chi-square value 5.258 is lesser than its tabulated value at 5 per cent level significance. Hence, there is no significant association between the respondents educational status and their level of awareness, knowledge and adoption of healthy life style practices in the study area.

Table No 4 Distribution of Education wise Respondents by their Level of Adopting Rescue Measures for Life Style Risks

Education	Level of Access			Total
	Low	Medium	High	
Middle	3 (1.0%)	56 (17.8%)	4 (1.3%)	63 (20.1%)
High School	7 (2.2%)	122 (38.9%)	27 (8.6%)	156 (49.75)
Higher Secondary	5 (1.6%)	72 (22.9%)	10 (3.2%)	87 (27.75)
College	0	8 (2.5%)	0	8 (2.5%)
Total	15 (4.8%)	258 (82.2%)	41 (13.1%)	314 (100.0%)

Calculate Chi-square Value	Degrees of Freedom	Level of Significance
7.076	6	0.314 (Not Significant)

It could be analysed only 13.1 per cent of the respondents irrespective of their educational background are having a high level of awareness and adopting rescue measures for life style risks and maintaining sustainable health.

The computed chi-square value 7.076 is lesser than its tabulated value at 5 per cent level of significance. Hence, there is no significant association between the respondents educational status and their level of awareness knowledge and adopting rescue measures for life style risks in the study area.

Conclusion

It is concluded from the investigation that the structural determinants of daily life contribute to the social determinants of health and nutritional inequalities in health between family and caste groups there is a need for greater and better integration of all human resource development programs both at the decision making level as well as at the implementation level. It is recommended the following to achieve positive health in rural areas, managing rural development with provision of affordable housing, clean water and sanitation in addition to addressing rural land tenure and livelihood is mandatory. The provision of fair and continuous employment and universal public distribution system are necessary. The establishment and strengthening of universal social protection schemes are called for continuation the current positive action in education and employment is crucial. Strengthening the Mid-day Meal scheme, the Sarva Shiksha Abiyan, Kishori Shakthi Yojana, Right to Education Act, MGNREGA, Food Security Act, NRHM, National Program for Adolescent Girls, and Rajiv Gandhi Scheme for Empowerment of Adolescent Girls, all steps in the right direction, is essential. There is a need to increase resource allocation for the social determinants of health and to reinforce the government's primary responsibility in providing for basic needs.

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